

The Role of Secondary School in The Development of the Values of Digital Citizenship for Students Under the Coronavirus Pandemic (Covid-19)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 30,2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Secondary School, Digital Citizenship, Coronavirus Pandemic</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4628349</p>	<p><i>The Coronavirus pandemic (Covid-19) led to the closure of schools and the stay of students in their homes, and the tendency of states to use distance and e-learning to educate their students at all levels of education, which imposes the need to instill the values of digital citizenship to give them behaviors and ethics of the safe and responsible use of digital technologies in education, so this study came to learn about the role of Secondary school in promoting the values of digital citizenship among students in Saudi Arabia under the Coronavirus pandemic, The study used the descriptive approach, and applied a questionnaire to a stratified random sample of (3591) male and female students in governmental and private secondary schools in the governorates of Dammam and Khobar. The study concluded that the secondary school has a major role in developing the values of digital citizenship for its students, and that there are statistically significant differences between the responses of the study sample at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.01$) in the role of the secondary school in developing the concept of digital citizenship according to the gender and school variables for both males and private schools.</i></p>

Introduction

During the current year 2020, the world witnessed an unprecedented health crisis during the past centuries and years, consisting of the emergence and rapid spread of the Coronavirus pandemic (Covid-19), which clearly affected the way of life of societies and states, disrupting their movement, losing their balance, shaking their economies, slowing their development, socializing among their members, and negatively affecting all sectors of health, education, economic, political and social.

Education is one of the sectors most affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, which led to the total or partial closure of schools in more than 190 countries, negatively affecting 1.7 billion students, representing about 94% of students worldwide, and forcing hundreds of millions of learners to stay at home (The World Bank, 2020), the UN report described as the longest school closure in the history of education.

The Corona virus pandemic (Covid-19) has forced academic bodies around the world to look for new types of education, using distance education, e-learning through educational platforms and social networks to provide education to students at various levels of education, and thus shifting the pattern of education from attending to indirect education (Abu Shakhaddim, 2020), and the digital school has emerged to provide educational service to its students, and students are dealing strongly with a digital world-unclear to laws and landmarks - without realizing the new role they play. As digital citizens, this world is full of many educational impositions, but at the same time it is not free of risks such as communicating with digital unknowns, browsing unknown or dangerous sites, and this confirms the Baily& Ribble (2007) that the digital world has only a few rules about appropriate and inappropriate behavior for the digital citizen, as (Algazar, 2014) asserts that the time spent by students in the face of digital technologies can be a major risk to them, especially in the absence of awareness of the rules of proper and safe use of these technologies.

Despite the importance of promoting the values of digital citizenship for students, the Corona virus pandemic has increased this importance even more, with digital technology being the only channel through which students receive education, and digital citizenship is the guide for students to provide them with appropriate and accept Table digital behaviors and practices, which Mossberger, (Toibert & McNwal, 2008) refer to as the ideal model for citizenship in the 21st century, as it reflects the appropriate and acceptTable standards of conduct associated with the use of dotter, which is considered to be the ideal model for citizenship in the 21st century (Hedges & Parker, 2016). A protective tool to protect students from the misuse of modern technologies and the Internet, and as a result (Ribble, 2011) has created a document to mitigate the dangers of digital technology, called the "Responsible Use Policy Document", which contains three categories of core values: respect, education and protection (REP) to teach students the rules of proper, accept Table and safe conduct in digital environments.

As a result, the instillation of the values of digital citizenship in Koruna's time has become a global orientation that has imposed itself on educational institutions, primarily the school as the primary responsibility for preparing students and giving them the ethical norms and behavioral standards necessary to deal with the digital world, as confirmed by the results of the Algazar's Study (2014). That the school provides students with a moral and value framework governing their practices in the digital world, the results of the Musalmani's Study (2014) which confirmed that the school trains its students in the responsible and ethical use of information technology, and the results of the Dahshan Study (2016) which confirmed However, life in the digital age requires schools to give their students a culture of rational and safe use of digital technologies, hence the results of studies (Abdul Razek, Nasr & Ibrahim, 2020; Aldarweish, 2020; Kafafi, 2018; Hashish, 2018; Zahrani, 2019) on the need to activate the school's role in instilling the values of digital citizenship in students to give them the behaviors and ethics that govern their dealings in the digital world.

Many studies have diagnosed reality by determining the level of digital citizenship among students in public education, such as the Study of (Al-Saadi, 2018), which emphasized that middle school in Saudi Arabia has an important role to play in promoting the values of digital citizenship among its students, and the Study of (Al-Ajami, Al-Hindal & Al-Atil, 2018), which emphasized the weak role of the curriculum in promoting digital citizenship in Kuwait, rather than the study (2016), which emphasized that basic education in Egypt promotes citizenship among its students to a medium degree.

Saudi Arabia is not immune from the global repercussions of the corona crisis on education. Schools were closed on 9 March 2020, it adopted distance and e-learning through educational platforms based on modern techniques in teaching students at different levels of education, and paved the way for the strong integration of students into the digital society with its positive risks, and students spend most of their time in front of digital technologies and the Internet, and this imposes the need to recognize the role of the secondary school in providing its students with the rules of employment and the criteria of responsibility. The safe and ethical of digital techniques in education after the emergence of the Coronavirus pandemic. The problem of study is determined by the following research question: What is the role of the secondary school in the development of the values of digital citizenship for its students under the Coronavirus pandemic (Covid-19)?

1. What role does Secondary school play in developing the values of digital citizenship for its students under the Coronavirus pandemic?
2. Does the role of secondary school in the development of the values of digital citizenship for its students change depending on the gender and type of school?

The results of this study will benefit the Ministry of Education, school principals, parents and students in identifying the role of secondary school in developing the values of digital citizenship for its students, and how to activate this role to give students the behaviors and ethics necessary to deal with the digital world.

Literature Review:

1.1 Digital citizenship:

The concept of digital citizenship is one of the modern concepts that emerged after the transformation of societies towards the digital age, which was characterized by the rapid progress in information and communication technology. Which resulted in many applications that affected different areas of life, and the evidence indicates that the emergence of this term is due to an article published by the International Association of Technology in Education in 2004 entitled Digital Citizenship: Addressing the Appropriate Behavior of Technology, where it adopted this concept as an attempt to prepare a regulation for the use of digital technology in a sound and security manner, and to develop a general framework for solving problems related to its use (ISTE, 2020).

(Ribble, 2011) defines digital citizenship as the rules of optimal and responsible use of technology, and (Farmer, 2011) defines it as the ability to use technology safely, responsibly, selectively, effectively and nationally.

The values of digital citizenship relate to the rules, standards and ethics necessary to deal with digital technologies, and (Dahshan, 2016) defines it as a set of controls and standards in the use of digital technology, which are a set of rights that citizens, young and old, should enjoy while using their technologies, The duties they must perform and adhere to during their use, as (Soldem, 2018) defines them as a set of appropriate and responsible rules and behaviors that must be followed while dealing with the digital world in order to improve the use and proper use of technology and the Internet.

In the light of the foregoing, digital citizenship is concerned with preparing students and providing them with standards and values that enable them to use modern technology and its advanced tools, and the values of digital citizenship are defined procedurally as a set of rules, standards and behavioral, ethical and legal controls that should be taught to students in schools. In order to respect themselves and others, educate themselves and communicate with others, and protect themselves and others in the digital community, it is clear from this definition that the values of digital citizenship include giving students the skills to help them deal with digital technology in a safe and secure manner, Their positive and responsible participation in the digital community,

their adherence to the ethical norms and legal disciplines prevailing in the digital society, and their protection from the dangers of the unconscious use of digital technologies.

2. 1 The importance of digital citizenship for students:

Awad (2016) identified the importance of digital citizenship for students in:

- Safe practice and responsible, legal and ethical use of information and technology.
- To acquire positive technology-using behavior that is characterized by collaboration, learning and productivity.
- Personal responsibility for lifelong learning.

Lyons (2012) noted that the importance of digital citizenship is to prepare the individual to be an active member of the global Internet community, Shahada & Ahmed (2019) identified the importance of digital citizenship in:

- Direct students to make the most of the positives of the digital world.
- Protecting students from the dangers of digital technologies.
- Developing awareness of rights, duties and responsibilities in the digital world.
- Preparing students to meet the challenges of the digital world with confidence, efficiency and innovative ways.
- Positive and effective participation in the digital world to contribute to the advancement of society.

3. 1 Digital Citizenship Values and Standards:

Several studies have indicated, including (Al-Dossary, 2017; Hashish, 2018; Isman & Canan, 2014; Ribble, 2014; Snyder, 2016), that digital citizenship includes three categories of key values: respect, Education or awareness, and protection (REP) that helps to promote the ethical and responsible behavior of the student, so that the protection shield is formed by the imam of the dangers of digital technologies, and these values are interconnected and interactive with each other, each of which includes three dimensions of digital citizenship, and this is explained below :

1.3.1 **Respect values:** it relates to self-respect and respect for others, and includes three dimensions:

- **Digital Etiquette:** the values and standards to be observed when using digital technologies, and the digital citizen's follow-up to the correct code of conduct in dealing with others in the digital society, so that it is an example to be followed by all.
- **Digital Access:** values and standards associated with full participation in the digital community, equal digital rights, and equal opportunity for all to access and use technology
- **Digital Laws:** values and standards that govern students' behavior's and practices within the digital community, such as intellectual property laws, patents, and information crime control systems, ensuring the integrity of their practices and properly carrying out their digital duties.

1.3.2 **The values of education and communication with others:** values associated with self-education, self-education and communication with others, and which include three dimensions:

- **Digital Communication :** values and standards associated with the exchange of electronic information, and communication with others via digital devices and technologies
- **Digital Literacy:** the standards and values associated with the education and learning of digital technology and understanding of its services and how to use them properly and safely in communication, communication and the completion of various transactions.
- **Digital Commerce:** the values and standards associated with financial transactions through the Internet and e-shopping.

1.3.3 **Protection values:** linked to the protection of oneself and others, and comprises three dimensions:

- **Digital Rights and Responsibilities:** the rules and laws governing the use of technology, ensuring the preservation of the rights of the digital citizen and others, and the handling of digital information in the correct and systematic manner.
- **Digital Security:** values and standards associated with prevention and electronic protection of personal information and data, protection of the property of others, and how to deal with negative messages received through digital technologies.
- **Digital Health and Wellness:** The standards and values associated with the healthy and proper use of digital technologies to maintain the physical and psychological health of the individual.

1.4 Stages of the development of digital citizenship values in schools:

The Corona virus pandemic (Covid-19) has led states to strongly integrate students into the digital world with its pros and cons, as their dealings with the digital world have imposed on them responsibilities and duties and, in turn, guaranteed them rights, and this imposes the need to pay attention to instilling the values of digital citizenship for students to give them the values, standards and ethics necessary to deal with the digital world and take advantage of its positive stake in the educational process.

The values of digital citizenship for students are developed to give them responsible, ethical and safe behavior in the use of digital technologies to be valid digital citizens through four integrated and interactive stages:

- **Awareness stage:** Educational institutions are interested in providing students with all that qualifies them to become fully familiar with the digital world and its various tools and media by informing them of the material components, software and basic knowledge of the digital world and its pros and cons (Ribble & Bailey, 2006).
- **Guided practice stage :** To allow students to use digital technology and its multiple tools properly and safely in a climate that encourages risk and discovery, under the supervision of teachers and school management.
- **Modeling stage and give the ideals and role models:** The stage means providing positive and ideal models for students on how to use digital technologies at home and at school, so that students can imitate and follow them (Shaaban, 2018).
- **Feedback and behavioral analysis:** At this stage, students are given the opportunity to discuss and criticize their use of digital technologies in classrooms, by giving them critical thinking skills to distinguish between proper and improper use of technology in and out of the classroom (Sharaf & Al-Demirdash, 2014).

Methodology

- 2.1 **The Study Approach:** The study used the survey descriptive method to collect data by applying a questionnaire to students to learn about the role of secondary school in promoting the values of digital citizenship for its students under the Coronavirus pandemic.
- 2.2 **Community of study:** The school community consists of students male and female students of governmental and private secondary schools in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, whose studies have shifted electronically after the closure of schools due to the corona pandemic.
- 2.3 **Sampling :** A random sample of (3591) male and female students was selected in governmental and private Secondary schools in Dammam and Khobar in the Kingdom Saudi Arabia.
- 2.4 **Questionnaire Design :** The study used a questionnaire consisting of two parts, section one: general information, and the second section the role of the school in the development of the values of digital citizenship, and it was divided into three dimensions: the first dimension measures respect values, it consists of (8) phrases, the second dimension measures the values of educating and communicating with others, it consists of (9) phrases, the third dimension measures protection values , it consists of (7) phrases, and The five-point Likert- type scale . the student answered the items by selecting one If the (5 Strongly Agree, 4 Agree, 3 Neutral, 2 Disagree, 1 Strongly Disagree) to categorize student responses.
- 2.5 **Validity:** The validity of the questionnaire was verified by presenting it to (9) experts, to identify their opinions in its dimensions and phrases, and it was modified in the light of their opinions, and the measure became in its final form consisting of (24) words, as the authenticity of the internal consistency of the questionnaire is verified, by calculating the Pearson's correlation coefficient between the grades of the phrases and The overall degree of dimension to which you belong, and the correlation coefficients ranged from the terms grades to the total score of the dimension of respect values (0.77-0.90), the dimension of the values of education (0.77-0.93), and the dimension of the protection values (0.74-0.93).
- 2.6 **Reliability:** The reliability of the questionnaire was verified by the calculation of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The reliability coefficient was for the dimension of respect values (0.97), for the dimension of the values of education (0.85), for the dimension of protection values (0.94) and for the questionnaire as a whole (0.94).
- 2.7 **Research procedures:** The questionnaire was prepared and confirmed its Validity and Reliability, it was applied electronically to government and private Secondary schools students in Saudi Arabia during October and November 2020.
- 2.7 **Data Analysis :** SPSS 21 statistical software was used to calculate Pearson's correlation coefficient to verify the validity of the questionnaire, calculate the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to verify the reliability of the questionnaire, calculate the mean and standard deviation of the dimensions and questionnaire statements, and calculate T-test to see the differences between the study variables, and Calculate of the effect size value by Cohen's d test.

To determine the degree of approval of sample members for the dimensions and phrases of the questionnaire, the value of the weight of the responses was calculated, and then there is a tendency to strongly disagree of the dimension or phrase if the Mean (1.79) is lower, and the trend is disagree if it is between (1.80-2.59), neutral if it is between (2.60-3.39), agree if it is between (3.40-4.19), and strongly agree if the mean (4.20) and above.

Results:

3.1 Results on the role of secondary school in the development of digital citizenship values for students:

The field study seeks to identify the role of Secondary school in developing the values of digital citizenship for its students under the Coronavirus pandemic, and the results are presented according to the dimensions and overall degree:

3.1.1 Results on the role of secondary school in the development of Total digital citizenship values:

Table 1 The Mean and the standard deviation of the role of Secondary school in the development of total digital citizenship values

NO	Dimensions	M	SD	Rank
1	Values of respect	3.90	0.74	1
2	values of Education and communication with others	3.87	0.81	2
3	Protection Values	3.83	0.89	3
Total digital citizenship values		3.87	0.75	

It can be seen from the Table 1; total digital citizenship values as a whole was $M=3.87$ and the standard deviation $SD=0.75$, the response score for the study sample came agree, and the mean of the dimensions of the digital citizenship values was between (3.83 - 3.09), and the standard deviation was between (0.74- 0.89) confirming a convergence in the opinions of the study sample, and that the values of digital citizenship with the highest mean are the values of respect $M=3.90$, followed by the values of education and communication with others $M=3.87$, and finally the protection values $M=3.83$.

3.1.2 Results on the role of secondary school in the development of the values of respect in the digital society:

Table 2 Mean and standard deviation of the role of secondary school in the development of the values of respect

No	Phrases	M	SD	Rank
1	Giving students habits of respecting the privacy of others in the digital community	4.04	0.88	3
2	Urge students to respect the views of others in the digital community	4.05	0.91	2
3	Urge students to respect the laws governing digital handling	4.19	0.82	1
4	Giving students the ethical standards that govern digital practices	4.01	0.87	4
5	Educating students about unacceptable behaviors in the digital community	3.78	1.19	6
6	Introducing students to penalties for digital crimes	3.75	1.18	7
7	Urge students to renounce violence and harassment against others in the digital community.	3.50	1.35	8
8	Give students values of respect for the rights of others' property in the digital community.	3.91	1.05	5
Total values associated with respect		3.90	0.74	

It can be seen from the Table 2; respect values statements is between (3.50-4.19), all of these averages are within the "agree" range, and the standard deviation is limited between (0.88-1.19) These values show a convergence in the views of the study sample in the role of the school in achieving the values of respect for its students, and that the phrases (3, 2), which read "Respect the laws in the digital society", "respect the views of others in the digital society", received the highest mean 4.19 ,4.05 occupied the first and second ranks. As for the two phrases (6, 7), which read "Know the penalties for digital crimes", "rejection of violence and harassment against others in the digital society", received the lowest mean (3.75, 3.5) and occupied the last two ranks.

3.1.3 Results on the role of secondary school in the development of the values of education and communication with others in the digital community:

Table 3 Mean and standard deviation of the role of secondary school in the development of the values of education and communication with others

No	Phrases	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Inform students of their digital rights and duties	4.05	0.96	2
2	Encourage students to adhere to ethical values in their dealings with the digital community.	4.17	0.88	1
3	Giving students the standards of communication in the digital community	4.01	0.91	3
4	Giving students the ability to analyze and criticize digital information sources	3.81	1.03	6

5	Give students the ability to dialogue in the digital community	3.90	1.01	4
6	Encourage students to share positive knowledge with others in the digital community	3.86	1.11	5
7	Give students the standards and values of a secure digital trade	3.65	1.14	8
8	Giving students the ability to rationalize digital shopping	3.57	1.13	9
9	Develop students' ability to think critically to distinguish between the good and the bad in the digital society.	3.81	1.05	6
Total values associated with education and communication with others		3.87	0.81	

It can be seen from the Table 3 the values of education and communication with others is limited to between (3.57-4.17), the standard deviation is limited to between (0.88-1.14), all of these averages are in the range "agree", and that the two Phrases (2 , 1) and the text "urge students to adhere to ethical values in dealing with the digital community", "Introducing students and their digital duties" received the highest mean 4.17, 4.05, and Ranked first and second, and the two Phrases (7, 8) and the text "Give students the standards and values of safe digital commerce", "giving students the ability to rationalize digital shopping" on the lowest mean account (3.65, 3.57) and Ranked last two ranks.

3.1.4 Results on the role of secondary school in the development of protection values in the digital community:

Table 4 Mean and standard deviation of the role of secondary school in the development of protection values

No	Phrases	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Introducing students to the psychological and physical risks of electronic addiction	3.63	1.19	7
2	Giving students standards for the proper and safe use of digital technologies	3.84	1.077	4
3	Educate students about the value of time during their digital transactions	3.81	1.07	5
4	Educate students on how to deal with misinformation in the digital community	3.77	1.06	6
5	Students urged to be credible in disseminating information during their digital transactions	3.98	1.01	1
6	Educating students about the danger of spreading rumors and circulating them through the digital community	3.85	1.13	3
7	Introducing students to ways to maintain personal identity and digital privacy in the digital community	3.89	1.11	2
Total protection values		3.83	0.89	

It can be seen from the Table 4 protection values phrases is limited between (3.63-3.98), all of which are located in the range "agree" , and the standard deviation is limited to between (1.01-1.19), these The values show a convergence in the sample's views on the role of Secondary school in instilling protection values among students, and that the two phrases (5 , 7) , which read "urge students to be credible in disseminating information during their digital dealings", "introducing students to ways to preserve personal identity and digital privacy" , got The highest mean (3.98, 3.89) occupied the first and second Ranked, while the two phrases (4,1) which read "Educating students about how to deal with misinformation in the digital community", "introducing students to the psychological and physical risks of electronic addiction", received the lowest mean (3.77, 3.63), and came in the last two ranks.

3.2 Results of differences between the means of students grades by two variables gender and school type:

3.2.1 Differences between study sample responses in the role of the school in the development of digital citizenship values by gender variable:

Table 6 The T- test between the mean of students depending on the gender variable.

Dimension	Gander	N	M	SD	df	T	P-value	D
Values of respect	Male	1884	4.01	0.69	3589	8.78	0.000	0.301
	Female	1707	3.79	0.77				
Values of education and communication with others	Male	1884	4.01	0.74	3589	11.84	0.000	0.38
	Female	1707	3.71	0.84				
Protection values	Male	1884	3.97	0.81	3589	10.21	0.000	0.34
	Female	1707	3.67	0.96				
Total digital citizenship values	Male	1884	3.99	0.68	3589	11.23	0.000	0.37
	Female	1707	3.72	0.79				

It can be seen from the Table 6 there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.01$) between male and female responses to the role of the school in achieving the total digital citizenship values and its three dimensions (values of respect, values of education, protection values) in favor of males, and The effect size of the Cohen d test is low, as it is between (0.30-0.37).

3.2.2 The differences between study sample responses in the role of the school in the development of digital citizenship values by variable school type:

Table 7 The T-test between the means of student's grades depending on the school type variable.

Dimension	School type	N	M	SD	dF	T	P-Value	d
Values of respect	Governmental schools	2577	3.84	0.74	3589	8.63	0.000	0.32
	Private schools	1014	4.07	0.69				
Values of education and communication with others	Governmental schools	2577	3.81	0.81	3589	7.13	0.000	0.27
	Private schools	1014	4.02	0.77				
Protection values	Governmental schools	2577	3.76	0.91	3589	6.70	0.000	0.25
	Private schools	1014	3.98	0.84				
Total digital citizenship values	Governmental schools	2577	3.80	0.76	3589	8.19	0.000	0.30
	Private schools	1014	4.02	0.70				

It can be seen from the Table 7 there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.01$) between the responses of students in governmental and private secondary schools about the role of the school in achieving the total digital citizenship values and its three dimensions (values of respect, values of education, protection values) for private schools, and The effect size of the Cohen d test is low, as it is between (0.27- 0.32).

Discussion:

4.1 The role of secondary school in developing the values of digital citizenship among its students:

- For Total digital citizenship values:

The results showed that students as a whole agreed that secondary schools have a high role in the development of total digital citizenship values under the Coronavirus pandemic ($M=3.87$), looking these results, we find that they were compatible and consistent with the educational reality. The Ministry of Education has adopted the system of distance and e-learning in providing education to students at home after the closure of schools due to the Coronavirus pandemic, and has provided programs and guides to students and used social media tools to spread the culture of proper and safe use of modern technology in education. This result is consistent with the results of the studies of (Aldarweish, 2020; Al-Saadi, 2018; Khalil, 2020) that emphasized the school's role in promoting the values of digital citizenship among students, is due to the Ministry of Education's interest in activating the role of secondary schools in promoting the role of digital citizenship for students further after the Coronavirus pandemic as the bulwark for students from the risks and negative effects of technical developments.

- For the values of respect:

It Ranked first from the point of view of the individuals of the sample ($M=3.90$), which confirms that secondary schools have a significant role in developing the values of respect among students, by urging them to respect digital laws, the rights of ownership of others, and respect for their opinions and Their particularity in the digital society, as well as urging them to renounce violence and harassment against others and give them ethical standards, and this result is consistent with the efforts of the Ministry of Education after the suspension of the study on March 16, 2020 and the adoption of electronic platforms in education from sending bulletins The messages of awareness and evidence to inform students of how to respect themselves and others during their digital dealings and practices, and this finding is consistent with the findings of my study (Al-Saadi, 2018; Khalil, 2020), which emphasized the role of the school in promoting the values of respect among students.

- For the values of education and communication with others:

It Ranked second from the perspective of the individuals of the sample ($M=3.87$), which is consistent with the efforts of the school administration after the Coronavirus pandemic to instill the values of education and communication among students to take advantage of the digital world and adhere to its practices, By providing programs through electronic educational platforms to encourage

students to adhere to the ethics of the digital world, to inform them of their digital rights and duties, to provide them with the standards of communication, dialogue and positive exchange of their knowledge with others, and to give them the ability to analyze the sources of digital information, and to rationalize the processes of Digital marketing, This result is consistent with the results of Khalil (2020) which emphasized that secondary education has a role to play in giving students the digital culture of education and communication with others.

– **For protection values:**

It came in third rank from the perspective of the individuals of the sample ($M=3.83$), which confirms the efforts of secondary schools to instill the values of protection among students from the dangers of modern technology after the Coronavirus pandemic to inform them of ways to preserve their data and personal information The psychological and physical risks of electronic addiction, the standards of proper and safe use of digital technologies, as well as their awareness of the value of time and the seriousness of the dissemination of misinformation and how to deal with it, This result is consistent with the results of Khalil (2020), which emphasized the role of Secondary school in promoting Students' values of protection towards themselves and others.

4.2 Differences between study sample responses according to gender variables, school type:

– **The Gender variable:**

The results showed statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.001$) between male and female sample responses to the role of the school in achieving digital citizenship values as a whole, and its subdimensions of values (citizenship, education, protection) in favor of males ($t=11.23$, $p=0.000$, $d= 0.37$) and with a small impact size, this finding is consistent with the findings of the Study of Al-Ajami, Al-Hindal & Al-Atil (2018), this result is due to the fact that males are more used to the digital world and social media tools and the Internet compared to females who have reservations To enter the digital world, males are therefore more aware of the role that secondary school play in providing them the behaviors and ethics for the safe and responsible use of digital technologies in education and protecting them from its risks.

– **The School variable:**

The results showed statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.001$ between the responses of students in governmental and private secondary schools in the role of the school in achieving the values of digital citizenship as a whole and its subdimensions in favor of private schools, ($t= 7.93$), $P=0.000$, $d=0.30$) and with a small impact size, this result is consistent with the findings of the Awad Study (2016), and this result is due to the interest of private schools in using social media tools to communicate with their students at home, and train them to enter the digital world and benefit from it in Education since the suspension of the study due to the Coronavirus pandemic, as well as providing programs, activities and direct support to its students to help them make the most of digital technologies and use them properly and safely and to give them the values and ethics associated with their practice.

Conclusions:

In the light of the results of the study, the following conclusions were reached:

- Secondary schools play a major role in promoting the values of digital citizenship for their students, which enable them to easily deal with the digital society with its different technologies after closing schools to take advantage of its pros and protect them from risk.
- private secondary schools have a greater role in promoting the values of digital citizenship for their students than in governmental schools, because they have been interested in training their students since joining them to take advantage of the digital society and its advanced technologies in education.
- Males are more aware of the role of secondary school in promoting the values of digital citizenship than females, because they frequently use the digital world, its techniques and advanced tools

Recommendations:

The study recommends:

- Teaching a specialized course on digital citizenship in secondary schools, including digital citizenship topics, fields and ethics, to give students proper digital behavior.
- The Ministry of Education issued laws and legislation to include the values of digital citizenship in the content of various courses such as computers, life skills, family education and languages.
- Integrating digital citizenship into the strategic plan of the Ministry of Education in Saudi Arabia and circulating it to public schools for implementation.

- Establishing an academic specialty in Saudi universities to graduate teachers specializing in digital citizenship to meet the needs of general education schools.

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